

On the origin of gravity and the emergence of a black hole

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Abstract

We show the theoretical origin of gravitational force and explain why it is the weakest force of nature. Further, we report that if the gravity of any object at any point is greater than a certain amount of gravitational force, from that point on it will be a black hole-like object; this might be a new criterion for being a black hole. It might offer fresh insight into the origin of gravity.

1 Introductions

Gravity is one of nature's four fundamental forces; it is weak in comparison to its counterpart forces such as nuclear force, electrostatic force, and weak force, but it governs the universe on a large scale. This force is also responsible for forming a black hole on a cosmic scale [1]. This is an inverse square law force and is tested at the millimetre length scale; beyond this, a quantum force or nuclear force comes into play. At this scale, the effect of gravity is negligible.

Gravity plays a major role, and it is universally accepted in classical and black hole physics. This force was quantified by Newton, and he proposed an empirical equation to estimate its numerical value. Therefore, there is no theoretical derivation of this force, so it's difficult to describe its nature and other properties theoretically. We have no idea how it came about. This complicates our understanding of why gravity works between masses and is always an attractive force, as well as many other related questions. It has been bothering physicists for years.

Many theories have been proposed to explain it [2] [3]; nonetheless, the problem persists. It is believed that the quantum theory of gravity may have an answer to those ques-

tions [4] [5] [6], but it is still in its development stage. However, in this paper, we take this question from another perspective and investigate the origin of gravity by using the law of thermodynamics.

2 Origins of gravitational force

In order to meet those question we derive an expression for the gravitational force. To do so, we use the theory of thermodynamics, where entropic force [7] can be described as follows:

$$\nabla F \nabla R = T \nabla S = \nabla E \quad (1)$$

where F is force R is space parameter T is temperature, and S is entropy. If we take the energy $E = mc^2$ where m denotes mass and c as speed of light, and by substituting it in Eq.(1), it will turn into followings,

$$F^2 = \frac{\nabla m^2 c^4}{\nabla R^2} \quad (2)$$

this shows the generalized entropic force. To find out the mathematical expression of force we use a novel scheme where we suppose that there are two categories of force and one of

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them is as following:

$$F \propto \frac{\nabla m^2}{\nabla R^2} \propto c^4 \quad (3)$$

and the other is,

$$F \propto \frac{1}{R^2} \propto m^2 c^4 \quad (4)$$

both categories of forces are different by nature.

From above expression we can figure out the dependency of force on variables. In order to find the exact expression of force, we need to remove proportionality by using some constants, however, let assume G is that constant. In this case, the Eq.(3) will result in the following.

$$F = \frac{Gm^2}{R^2} = \frac{c^4}{G} \quad (5)$$

by dimensional analysis, we found the dimension of used constant G is same as the Newton's gravitational constant. Thus, we have recovered the mathematical expression for classical gravitational force. This shows the theoretical origin of gravitational force.

Similarly, the other category of force also needs to be remove the proportionality. For this category of forces, the used constant G is not work because the used variable are different, so by dimensional analysis, the constant that can eliminate the proportionality is hc , where h corresponds to the Planck constant and c denotes the speed of light. By substituting it in Eq.(4), it yields the following:

$$F = \frac{hc}{R^2} = \frac{m^2 c^4}{hc} \quad (6)$$

these forces are different from the classical gravitational force, and they can be used to estimate the numerical value of nuclear force [8], which is a quantum form of force. We are not going into its details since it's beyond the scope of this paper.

3 Why is gravity such a weak force of nature?

Now, we shown the theoretical origin of both gravitational and quantum force. And, as we discussed earlier, out of the four fundamental forces of nature, gravity is the weakest one, but the reason behind this fact is not clear. Here we give a heuristic interpretation of this fact.

Mathematically and dimensionally, we can re-write the Eq.(2) by using the Eq.(5) and (6) as follows [9]:

$$\underbrace{G \frac{m^2}{R^2} \times \frac{c^4}{G}}_{\text{Gravitational force side}} = \underbrace{\frac{hc}{R^2} \times \frac{m^2 c^4}{hc}}_{\text{Quantum force side}} \quad (7)$$

by substituting the mass m and R as the mass of proton and radius of nucleus, one can observe that there exists a large constant force $\left(\frac{c^4}{G}\right)$ on the gravitational side of the balance where its numerical value is nearly $\sim 10^{43}N$; thus, to retain the numerical balance, gravity remains weak.

This Eq.(7) can facilitate to derive the gravitational coupling constant (relative strength) as,

$$G \frac{m^2}{R^2} = \left(\frac{Gm^2}{hc}\right) \frac{hc}{R^2}$$

it corresponds to,

$$G \frac{m^2}{R^2} = \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_G}\right) \frac{hc}{R^2}$$

where α_G is gravitational coupling constant which shows the relative strength of gravity to nuclear force (strong force). This is already known thus it shows the consistency of our derived expression with other existing theory.

This also gives the idea that why is gravity a function of both mass and space, probably due to the existence of constant force terms in the Eq.(7), it retain the dimensional balance with quantum force. However, we infer there might close link between the weakness of gravity and it's dependency on variables.

4 On the relation between mass m and space R and the emergence of a black hole

The preceding section suggests the gravitational force side is dominant by the existence of constant force terms $\left(\frac{c^4}{G}\right)$; however, an obvious question is “what will happens if the gravitational force of any physical body/object becomes larger than that constant force?” Specifically, if the condition is as following,

$$\frac{c^4}{G} \leq \frac{Gm^2}{R^2}$$

simply it will reduce to,

$$R \leq \frac{Gm}{c^2} \quad (8)$$

this shows the relationship between the mass and radius of any given physical body/object at the condition when gravitational attraction force is very large.

This derived relation corresponds to the half the Schwarzschild radius of a black hole [10]. However, one can say that at that condition, that physical object becomes a black hole like object, and theoretically a black hole emerged. This gives us a new interpretation of a black hole’s event horizon. For any object, at any point if the gravity is $\leq \frac{c^4}{2G}$, it turn into a black hole.

Still a question persists why the mass is trapped in that condition, why matter can’t escape from a black hole, this needs to be answer.

5 Uncertainty relation between the mass and size of a black hole

In this line, it would be worthy to discuss that, on the basis of the above description, one may

speculate that the Eq.(8) might show the gravitational uncertainty relation similar to an uncertainty relation exists in quantum physics [11]. It means to say that the mass and radius of black holes can be gravitational conjugate variables. If this is so, then:

$$\frac{\nabla R}{\nabla m} \leq \frac{G}{c^2} \quad (9)$$

it denotes the gravitational uncertainty relation between ∇R and ∇m , and thus we infer that we can’t measure the size and mass of a black hole at the same time.

6 Conclusions

Gravity is an entropic force. We found that there is a natural balance between gravitational and quantum forces. But there exists a constant force $\left(\frac{c^4}{G}\right)$ with a high numerical value on the side of gravitational force; thus, to strike a balance, gravity becomes weak, giving us a mathematical explanation of the weakness of gravity.

The other implication of this constant force is that it shows the minimum gravity at any point of the object for a given mass and radius to be a black hole. Once the gravity is higher than this limit, the object will attain the Schwarzschild radius and turn into a black hole-like object. It gives a new perspective on the nature of gravity.

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